

NIGERIAN SOCIETY FOR CONSERVATION BIOLOGY

9th Biodiversity Conservation Conference
(2nd Virtual Edition)

Theme: Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Prospects

Time: 11 am - 3 pm

with support from

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

3 - 5 November 2025

EDITORS

Emmanuel C. Chukwuma, Fatsuma Olaleru Ph.D, Joy O. Arabomen Ph.D,
Adewale G. Awoyemi Ph.D & Abubakar S. Ringim Ph.D

© Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology

Published November 2025. The Proceedings of 9th Biodiversity Conservation Conference

NSCB 9th Biodiversity Conservation Conference 2025

The 9th Biodiversity Conservation Conference of the Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB), held virtually from 3–5 November 2025, brought together conservation experts, practitioners, researchers, and students to deliberate on the theme “*Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Future Prospects.*” As the second virtual edition in the conference series, the event featured five sub-themes addressing citizen science, community engagement, media and technology, youth involvement, conservation education impacts, and future pathways. The conference attracted 286 registered participants and received 47 abstracts and 28 full papers, with 32 technical presentations showcasing innovative research and conservation practices. Highlights included a keynote address by Dr. Joseph Onoja (Director-General, Nigerian Conservation Foundation) on vulture conservation in Nigeria, and a plenary lecture by Prof. Tijjani Sabiu Imam (Bayero University, Kano) on the challenges of upgrading protected areas, using Falgore National Park as a case study.

Theme: Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Future Prospects

Sub-Themes:

- Citizen Science and Community Engagement in Environmental Education
- The Role of Media and Technology in Biodiversity Conservation
- Youth Involvement in Promoting Biodiversity Conservation
- Future Pathways for Conservation Education in Nigeria
- Evaluating the Impact of Conservation Education in Nigeria

Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology: Executive Members

Olaleru Fatsuma <i>Ph.D.</i>	President
Ringim Abubakar S. <i>Ph.D.</i>	President-Elect
Raji Islamiat Abidemi <i>Ph.D.</i>	General Secretary
Popoola Shola Caleb	Assistant Secretary
Arabomen Joy O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Financial Secretary

Local Organizing Committee Members

Olaleru Fatsuma <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Lagos, Yaba	President
Awoyemi Adewale <i>Ph.D.</i>	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan	Chairman
Agbo Boniface O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Kaduna State University, Kaduna	Secretary
Ringim Abubakar S. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Federal University Dutse, Jigawa State	
Arabomen Joy O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan	
Suberu Adebukola (Mrs.)	Lagos State Ministry of Environment & Water Resources	
Adepegba Victoria A <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Ibadan, Ibadan	
Oyegbami Akinleye I.	Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta	
Arch. Bage John B.	Federal University of Lafia, Nasarawa State	
Chukwuma Emmanuel C.	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan	
Ibrahim Ahmad <i>Ph.D.</i>	Bauchi State Government	
Magaji Aisha S. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Northwest University Kano	
Ezenwa Ifeanyi	University of Nigeria Nsukka	

Sub-committees

Programme & Speakers

Chukwuma Emmanuel C.
Ezenwa Ifeanyi
Adepegba Victoria Ajeyinka *Ph.D.*

Publicity & Media

Oyegbami Akinleye Isaac
Adepegba Victoria Ajeyinka *Ph.D.*

Documentation & Reporting

Magaji Aisha Sani *Ph.D.*
Arch. Bage John Bege

Finance & Admin

Ibrahim Ahmed *Ph.D.*
Adebukola Suberu (Mrs.)

Abstract and/or Manuscript Reviewers

Abdu Salamatu <i>Ph.D.</i>	Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
Abdulfatai Babatunde R <i>Ph. D.</i>	Osun State University, Osogbo
Adepegba Victoria A <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Ibadan, Ibadan
Agbo Boniface O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Kaduna State University, Kaduna
Agwu Patrick O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Osun State University, Osogbo
Ajao Abdulwakeel <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Ajayi Benjamin A.	Florida State University, US
Akinyemi Idongesit G <i>Ph.D.</i>	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan
Arabomen Joy O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan
Arch. Bage John B.	Federal University of Lafia, Nasarawa State
Asinwa Israel O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan
Awoyemi Adewale <i>Ph.D.</i>	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan
Chukwuma Deborah M. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti
Chukwuma Emmanuel C.	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan
David Oyinate <i>Ph.D.</i>	Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti
Ezenwa Ifeanyi	University of Nigeria Nsukka
Ibrahim Ahmad <i>Ph.D.</i>	Bauchi State Government
Magaji Aisha S. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Northwest University Kano
Olaleru Fatsuma <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Lagos, Yaba
Olusanya Olatunji <i>Ph.D.</i>	Osun State University, Osogbo
Oluwole Pelemo J. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Ibadan
Onofeli Alfred O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Ibadan, Ibadan
Oyebanji Oyetola <i>Ph.D.</i>	University of Lagos, Yaba
Oyegbami Akinleye I.	Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta
Ringim Abubakar S. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Federal University Dutse, Jigawa State
Suberu Adebukola (Mrs.)	Lagos State Ministry of Environment & Water Resources
Tanimo Yahuza O. <i>Ph.D.</i>	Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Editors

Chukwuma Emmanuel C.
Olaleru Fatsuma *Ph.D.*
Arabomen Joy O. *Ph.D.*
Awoyemi Adewale *Ph.D.*
Ringim Abubakar S. *Ph.D.*

Table of Contents

NSCB 9th Biodiversity Conservation Conference 2025..... **ii**

Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology: Executive Members..... **iii**

Local Organizing Committee Members..... **iii**

Sub-committees..... **iii**

Abstract and/or Manuscript Reviewers..... **iv**

Table of Contents..... **v**

Welcome Speech by the Chairman, Local Organising Committee..... **vii**

Welcome Speech by the President, Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology **viii**

Brief profile of Dr. Joseph Onoja – Keynote Speaker **x**

Brief profile of Professor Tijjani Sabiu Imam – Plenary Speaker **xi**

Brief profile of Dr. Abubakar S. Ringim – NSCB President Elect..... **xii**

Goodwill messages from CaRE-NGO, Kaduna..... **xiii**

Goodwill messages from the Kano State Zoological and Wildlife Management Agency..... **xiv**

The Future of Vultures in Nigeria: Nigerian Conservation Foundation’s Awareness Campaigns for their Conservation..... **1**

SUB-THEME 1: CITIZEN SCIENCE AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION..... 5

 Ecotourism and Crocodile Management in the Niger Delta: Community Engagement and Educational Strategies for Sustainable Conservation **5**

 Survey of Shea Butter (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) Value Chain Actors in Northcentral Nigeria: Demographics and Constraints **18**

 Isolation and Identification of Fungi from Gurasa sold in Kaduna State University Main Campus u/rimi **24**

 Demand for Bitter Kola in Southwestern Nigeria **29**

 Comparative Studies of Birds in relation to their Utilization of *Mangifera indica* and *Parkia biglobosa* Trees in Jacaranda Farms, Kaduna, Nigeria **35**

 Abundance and diversity of birds' life along River Kaduna, Kaduna, Nigeria **44**

 Ecological and Socio-Economic Outcomes of Reforestation and Afforestation for Biodiversity Conservation on rural livelihoods in Southwest Nigeria **57**

 Abundance and Diversity of Migratory Birds in Relation to Weather Parameter in Ahmadu Bello University Dam, Zaria – Nigeria **63**

SUB-THEME 2: THE ROLE OF MEDIA AND TECHNOLOGY IN BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION..... 73

 Leveraging Digital Technologies for Conserving Animal Habitats in Nigeria’s Tropical Forests: An Opinion Perspective..... **73**

A Review of the Role of Environmental Factors on Plant Biodiversity, Conservation, and Innovative Extraction Procedures: A Focus on Nigerian Medicinal flora.....	77
Engaging Young People in Conservation Education through Digital Media and Technology: A Case Study of the University of Lagos Society for Ecological Restoration, Nigeria.....	82
Assessing the Role of the Media in Biodiversity Conservation in Nigeria	93
SUB-THEME 3: YOUTH INVOLVEMENT IN PROMOTING BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION.....	99
Environmental Education and Youth Participation in Biodiversity Conservation in Nigeria: a Review	99
A Review of Riparian Tree Species in the Flora of Nigeria.....	106
Youth Awareness and Participation in Biodiversity Restoration at Nigerian Defence Academy, Ribadu Cantonment, Kaduna, Nigeria	114
SUB-THEME 4: FUTURE PATHWAYS FOR CONSERVATION EDUCATION IN NIGERIA.....	121
Assessing the Social Drivers of Public Awareness and Perceptions of Climate Change in Nigeria....	121
Beyond Awareness: How Education and Income Shape Forest Conservation in Onigambari Forest Reserve, Nigeria	132
Effect of Chromium on the Behaviour and Blood Glucose Levels of <i>Clarias gariepinus</i>	138
The Need for Environmental Conservation Education in Igedeland.....	146
Genetic Provenance of a Captive Lion Population in Nigeria: Implications for Conservation and Management	159
Economic Assessment of Conservation Practices Among Farmers: A Pathway to Sustainable Agriculture in Nigeria.....	167
Scrap Metal Dumpsites as Unintentional Reservoirs of Plant Diversity: Insights for Conservation Education in Nigeria.....	175
Community Participation and Conservation Education Pathways for Sustainable Management of Osho Forest Reserve	183
SUB-THEME 5: EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF CONSERVATION EDUCATION IN NIGERIA.....	195
Environmental Conservation Educational Programs Among Secondary School Students in Oyo State, Nigeria	195
Designated Trail Efficacy for Avifauna Conservation on Roseberry Topping, North Yorkshire, England	201
Ecological Status of Mangrove Ecosystems in Ikorodu West LCDA Lagos: The Role of Conservation Education in Ensuring Protection	215
The Role of Conservation Education in Biodiversity Protection: Insights from Okomu National Park, Edo State, Nigeria.....	227
Two Decades of Vegetation Dynamics in Kamuku National Park, Nigeria: A Remote Sensing-Based Analysis of Land Cover Change.....	236

Welcome Speech by the Chairman, Local Organising Committee

Dear Conference Participants,

As Chairman of the Local Organizing Committee (LOC) for the 9th Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB) Conference (Second Virtual Edition), I am delighted to welcome you to this landmark event, scheduled to hold from 3rd – 5th November 2025.

The NSCB, a member of the global Society for Conservation Biology, continues to champion the advancement of conservation science, sustainable management, and public awareness of Nigeria’s rich yet threatened biodiversity. This year’s theme, “Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Future Prospects,” underscores our shared responsibility to nurture environmental consciousness and empower present and future generations to take meaningful action for nature.

Conservation education is not merely about knowledge; it is about transformation. Through this conference, we seek to bridge research, policy, and community engagement, fostering innovative approaches that connect classrooms, local communities, and national initiatives toward a sustainable and biodiverse Nigeria.

On behalf of the Local Organizing Committee, I extend my heartfelt appreciation to all committee members and the NSCB Executive Council for their dedication, teamwork, and tireless efforts in bringing this vision to life. I also express sincere gratitude to our sponsors and partners for their generous support, and to our distinguished Keynote and Plenary Speakers for sharing their time, wisdom, and inspiration.

I look forward to the thought-provoking discussions, innovative ideas, and inspiring presentations that participants will bring to this conference. Together, may our collective insights and collaborations strengthen conservation education and help secure a sustainable future for Nigeria’s biodiversity.

Dr. Adewale G. Awoyemi

Chairman, Local Organizing Committee
9th NSCB Conference (Second Virtual Edition)
Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology
(NSCB)

Welcome Speech by the President, Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology

The Board members of the Society for Conservation Biology (SCB), Global Office,
The Board members of the Society for Conservation Biology, Africa Region (SCB-AR),
The Board of Trustees, Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB),
The Keynote speaker, Dr. Joseph Onoja, DG/CEO Nigerian Conservation Foundation,
The Plenary speaker, Prof. Tijjani, S. Imam
Esteemed Executives members of NSCB
Distinguished members of the NSCB,
Conservation and excellence service award recipients,
Esteemed conference participants,
Gentlemen of the Press (both print and electronic),
Invited Guests, Ladies and Gentlemen.

It is with great privilege, honour, and delight that I welcome you to the **9th/2nd Virtual Biodiversity Conservation Conference** hosted by the Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB). In 2023 we held the **8th Biodiversity Conservation Conference** jointly organized by the Nigeria Tropical Biology Association and the

NSCB. It was a physical/virtual meeting that gave us the opportunity to interact and share ideas with members of the two hosting bodies. This virtual conference will still give us the opportunity to interact and collaborate as we present our research findings and field experiences.

The conference aims at advancing the science and practice of conserving Nigeria's biological diversity through the application of conservation science and management, and public education. Distinguished speakers and participants from the academia, conservation-based organisations, policy makers, local community advocacy, and private sectors are participating to promote awareness and advance action(s) for biodiversity conservation and the environment. Since the conference is not only for NSCB members, through it, we hope to support in capacity building of others as we also learn from them. The keynote and plenary speakers are seasoned conservationists that would share with us from the wealth of experiences and spur us to more practical actions.

The theme of this conference is "**Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Future Prospects**". It has five sub-themes: Citizen Science and Community Engagement, Media and Technology in Conservation, Youth Involvement in Biodiversity Conservation, Future Pathways for Conservation Education, and Evaluating Conservation Education Impacts. The theme and sub-theme present us with diverse ways of engaging citizen scientists, youths, and technology in achieving environmental conservation and education.

We received 47 abstracts spread across the five sub-themes. The spread is as follows: Citizen Science and Community Engagement, 18; Media and Technology in Conservation, 6; Youth Involvement in Biodiversity Conservation, 4; Future Pathways for Conservation Education, 12; and Evaluating Conservation Education Impacts,

7. For the conference Book of Proceedings, 29 manuscripts were received. Over 280 participants signed up to join the conference. Consequently, we are looking forward to diverse, engaging, and enriching conservation and environmental discourses.

This year, in recognizing the conservation efforts of individuals and organisations, we are giving five awards in three categories. These are: Leadership Excellence which goes to Dr. Adedotun O. Afolayan, the immediate past President of NSCB and President-Elect SCB-AR; Youth Mentorship and Conservation goes to Salamatu Jidda-Fada PhD, DSc (Hon), *FNES*; and Excellence in Conservation awards went to three organisations. These are Nigerian Conservation Foundation (NCF), Africa Nature Investors (ANI) Foundation, and World Conservation Society (WCS), Nigeria.

The NSCB is one of the strongest Chapters in the Africa Region. Her members are highly placed in the conservation community. Membership is open to all Nigerians, and foreigners working in biodiversity conservation in the country. Her previous conferences were held in Universities in southern Nigeria, viz: University of Ibadan (2010, 2012), University of Lagos (2013, 2023), Federal University of Technology, Akure (2015), University of Ilorin (2016), University of Uyo (2018), and First and Second Virtual Conferences (2020, 2025). We look forward to having universities in the north and east to host us in future conferences. Workshops held during these events were geared towards building capacity of young people, who have become prominent conservationists.

The planning of this conference was carried out by the Local Organising Committee. I really appreciate the efforts and time sacrificed towards the success of the conference. All the abstracts and manuscripts reviewers are appreciated. I thank the keynote and plenary speakers for accepting our invitation and giving time out of their tight schedules to be with us. The support of our sponsors is appreciated. The NSCB's Board

of Trustees, the SCB-AR Board, and SCB Global Office are appreciated for their support and guidance. To all who in some ways have contributed to the success of this conference, I am most grateful.

As the outgoing President of the NSCB, I want to use this opportunity to thank the SCB leaders at the Global and Regional levels, BOT members, great NSCB executives and members for giving me the opportunity to lead. I learnt a lot during these four years, first as President-Elect and as the President. I am still available for other assignments that I might be requested to handle. Finally, on behalf of the executives and esteemed members of NSCB, I welcome you again to this virtual conference. I wish us a purposeful, progressive and profitable conference and future endeavours.

Thank you all.

Fatsuma Olaleru, PhD.

President, Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology

Director, Young Women in Conservation Biology, SCB-AR

Brief profile of Dr. Joseph Onoja – Keynote Speaker

Dr. Joseph Onoja is the current Director-General of the Nigerian Conservation Foundation (NCF), which is the BirdLife International Partner in Nigeria, an Associate of WWF, and an organizational member of the IUCN. Dr. Onoja has achieved numerous successes in developing and managing conservation programs, building relationships with key stakeholders, and securing funding. His expertise cuts across community-based conservation, protected area management, ornithology, project management, climate change advocacy and practice, conservation administration, evidence-based research, and policy expertise. Dr. Onoja received his PhD in Conservation Biology from the University of Jos (Nigeria), specializing in the study of large raptors in and around the Yankari Game Reserve, a biodiversity haven in the northern savannah of Nigeria. At Yankari, he gained enormous first-hand experience on the effectiveness of

conservation actions that involve host communities, having worked with them on several occasions. These experiences were vital during the implementation of the strategic action plan to bring back West African vulture species from the brink of extinction, led in Nigeria by NCF under his able leadership as the Director of Technical Programmes. One remarkable innovation generated by Dr. Onoja to save vultures was his replacement of belief-based use of vulture parts in traditional medicine with the sustainable use of plant-based alternatives, and championing targeted awareness-raising campaigns. In addition to the vulture project, Dr. Onoja oversaw the implementation of other donor-funded activities across Nigeria, amounting to \$300,000 per annum. This has increased substantially to about \$1,000,000 in his current position as the substantive Director General. Dr Onoja will deliver the keynote lecture for this conference, entitled “*The Future of Vultures in Nigeria: NCF's Awareness Campaigns for Conservation*”, highlighting critical conservation issues and potential solutions.

Brief profile of Professor Tijjani Sabiu Imam

– Plenary Speaker

Ladies and Gentlemen,

Permit me to introduce the presenter of today's plenary paper titled *“Upgrade of Protected Areas and Its Challenges: A Case Study of Falgore National Park, Kano, Northern Nigeria.”*

Early Life and Education

Professor Tijjani Sabiu Imam hails from Dawaki, Dawakin Tofa Local Government Area of Kano State. Born into the family of Sheikh Sabiu Imam in the early 1970s, he began with Qur'anic and Islamic studies before pursuing formal education at Special Primary School, Dawakin Tofa; Government Arabic Junior Secondary School, Dunawa; and Science Secondary School, Kafin Hausa.

He obtained his Registered Nursing (RN) certificate from the College of Nursing, Kano (1990–1994), and later earned his B.Sc. in Applied Biology, M.Sc. in Parasitology, and Ph.D. in Environmental Biology from Bayero University, Kano (2002–2013). He has also received professional certifications in DNA Technology, Remote Sensing, GIS, Malaria Diagnostics, HIV Counseling, and Education.

Academic and Professional Career

Professor Imam began his career as a Clinical Instructor at the College of Nursing, Kano, before joining Family Health International in 2007 as an Assistant Counseling and Testing Officer under the GHAIN Project. Later that year, he joined Bayero University, Kano, where he rose through the ranks to become Professor of Environmental Biology in 2023. He has served as Head of Department, Postgraduate Coordinator, and member of the University Senate, and has participated in numerous departmental and faculty committees.

He has been an external examiner to several Nigerian universities and served as a Sabbatical Scholar at Yusuf Maitama Sule University and currently at Baba-Ahmed University, Kano. He has chaired and presented at many national and international conferences, including the NTBA Conference (2019) and CDA's 3rd International Conference on Dryland Agriculture (2018).

Research and Publications

Professor Imam has supervised over 100 undergraduate and 30 postgraduate projects, including several Ph.D. theses. He has authored and co-authored more than 100 peer-reviewed papers, four books, and numerous conference papers. He serves on several editorial boards and as a reviewer for national and international journals. His research focuses on ecology, conservation, environmental biology, and public health.

Affiliations and Interests

He is a member of the Society for Animal and Environmental Biology, Nigerian Biological Safety Association, Nigerian Environmental Society, and the Society for Conservation Biology.

Professor Imam is happily married with five children. His hobbies include aerobics, jogging, scrabble, and following environmental issues.

**Brief profile of Dr. Abubakar S. Ringim –
NSCB President Elect**

Dr. Abubakar S. Ringim is a dedicated and accomplished biodiversity conservationist who is deeply passionate about protecting the environment. He holds a BSc in Zoology from Bayero University Kano, an MSc in Biodiversity Conservation from the University of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, and a PhD in Bioenvironmental Sciences from Morgan State University, USA. He co-founded the Federal University Dutse (FUD) Conservation Society and currently serves as its Secretary. He is the Deputy Director at FUD's Centre for Arid Zone and Wetlands Ecology. Ringim plays key roles in several conservation organisations, including serving as Vice President/President-Elect of the Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB). He has served and is currently serving on many national committees, including the Technical Working Group for the Development and Implementation of a Wildlife Disease Surveillance System for Emerging and Re-

emerging Zoonotic Diseases and the National Coordination Group for Key Biodiversity Areas.

He is a member of the Nigerian Field Society and the West African Ornithological Society. In his administrative capacities, Ringim is the Chairman of the FUD Zoological Garden and the Deputy Coordinator for Postgraduate Programs in the Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, among other responsibilities. His research centres on biodiversity conservation and citizen science. Ringim has published numerous peer-reviewed articles and online content on biodiversity conservation and has participated in various national and international conferences. Beyond his professional work, he is an adventurer and nature photographer who uses his passion to inspire others in conservation. Ringim has traveled far and wide, and in this conference, participants will discover the tourist and cultural attractions in Nigeria through the amazing travels and tours of Ringim. www.abubakaringim.com

Goodwill messages from CaRE-NGO, Kaduna

On the occasion of the 9th/2nd Virtual Biodiversity Conservation Conference hosted by the Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB), the management and entire team of CaRE-NGO, Kaduna, extend our heartfelt felicitations to NSCB.

We commend the Society for her steadfast commitment to advancing the science and

practice of conservation in Nigeria. At a time when our natural ecosystems face unprecedented challenges, from habitat loss and climate change to biodiversity decline, this conference offers a critical platform for dialogue, collaboration, and innovative solutions.

As an organization dedicated to community-driven environmental resilience and sustainable development, CaRE-NGO shares deeply in NSCB's vision of a Nigeria where people and nature coexist in harmony. We are confident that the outcomes of this gathering will further strengthen national efforts toward biodiversity protection and sustainable resource management.

We wish all participants fruitful deliberations and a successful conference. May the ideas shared here inspire transformative actions for a greener, safer, and more sustainable Nigeria.

For and on behalf of CaRE-NGO, Kaduna,
Prof. Bala Dogo
Coordinator

Goodwill messages from the Kano State Zoological and Wildlife Management Agency

Standing on existing protocol,

It is with great pleasure and high esteem that I, on behalf of the Management and Staff of Kano State Zoological and Wildlife Management Agency (KAZOWMA), convey our heartfelt goodwill message to the Nigerian Society for Conservation Biology (NSCB) on this auspicious occasion of your bi-ennial conference.

We commend the NSCB for its unwavering commitment to the scientific study and conservation of biological diversity in Nigeria and beyond.

The choice of the theme, "Environmental Conservation Education in Nigeria: Current Status and Future Prospects," is both timely and critical. It resonates deeply with our core mandate at KAZOWMA, where we recognize that public education and awareness are paramount to effective conservation efforts.

Zoological gardens, National parks, Sanctuaries and Game & Forest Reserves, like ours in Kano, serve as a

vital living laboratory for environmental education, providing a unique platform for the public to connect with nature and understand the importance of wildlife conservation. We believe that enhancing the quality and delivery of these education programmes is crucial to fostering a conservation culture among our citizens, particularly the younger generation.

The current status of environmental awareness in Nigeria, thus improving in some areas, still presents significant challenges, including habitat degradation, poaching, and climate change impacts. This conference offers an invaluable opportunity for stakeholders, professionals, and students to deliberate on these issues and identify practical, innovative strategies to tackle them head-on.

As we look towards the future prospects of environmental conservation education, we must leverage new technologies, strengthen collaborations between government agencies, NGOs, and academic institutions to integrate conservation education into our formal and informal learning systems.

The insights and recommendations that will emerge from your discussions will undoubtedly shape policies and actions for a more sustainable future for our nation.

The KAZOWMA is committed to partnering with the NSCB and all relevant stakeholders to ensure that Nigerians prosper while living in harmony with nature.

I wish you a successful and fruitful conference.

Thank you and God bless.

Signed:

Conservator Sadik Kura Mohammed,
Managing Director, KAZOWMA

Engaging Young People in Conservation Education through Digital Media and Technology: A Case Study of the University of Lagos Society for Ecological Restoration, Nigeria

Franklin Ebelechukwu^a, Excellence Akeredolu^b, Deborah Iwalola Johnson-Opeseitan^c, Ayotilewa Motunrayo Fasusi^a, Fola Bakare^a Godspower Pere Toikumo^a, Ajao Shukurat Opeyemi^a, Ogungibe Abosede Beatrice^a, Ogberefor Michaeland^a, Ayegbusi Peter Oluwaseun^a, Abraham Aminu^a and Fakunmoju Folayemi Fawaz^a

^a *Society for Ecological Restoration, University of Lagos, Student Chapter.*

^b *Department of Zoology, University of Lagos, Nigeria*

^c *National Biotechnology Development Agency*

***Corresponding Author: franklinebelechukwu@gmail.com**

Abstract

Conservation education is an essential tool for protecting biodiversity by increasing public awareness, enhancing the understanding of environmental challenges, and inspiring individuals to take sustainable action. Conservation education is particularly crucial in addressing key conservation issues where survival depends on public knowledge, attitude shifts, and shared responsibility. Youth play a vital role in this effort, as their creativity, cultural awareness, and digital skills make them effective advocates for raising awareness about conservation challenges. Involving the youth in participatory initiatives ensures that topics on conservation are both well understood and culturally meaningful. In today's digital age, media and technology provide powerful platforms to amplify these efforts, reflecting local realities while aligning with global trends. This study engaged 50 student members from the University of Lagos Society for Ecological Restoration, representing diverse academic disciplines, who received hands-on training in media production and digital technologies, including video editing, animation, photography, blogging, and social media strategy. Building on this training, the participants designed and implemented a 30-day multi-platform campaign focused on pangolin conservation. Data were collected through platform analytics (Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and WordPress) and audience feedback forms to evaluate the effectiveness of different media formats, perceptions of content quality, and willingness to engage with conservation messages. Results showed that short videos, reels, and animations achieved the highest engagement, with YouTube leading in comments and likes, and Instagram excelling in shares. Posters were preferred by respondents mindful of data consumption, while blogs reached a niche audience. Feedback indicated increased awareness, support, and positive perceptions, all of which can significantly motivate lasting pro-environmental behaviors.

Keywords: Conservation Education, Endangered Species, Pangolin, Youth Participation, Media and Technology, Biodiversity Conservation, Environmental Awareness.

INTRODUCTION

Conservation education is the teaching and learning process that is meant to enhance people's knowledge, attitudes, and inspire them to protect, manage, restore, and sustainably use natural resources and ecosystems (USDA, 2023). It takes a comprehensive approach aimed at increasing public awareness and encouraging active involvement in environmental protection (Patra & Bhoi, 2025). It involves teaching individuals about the significance of biodiversity and the threats it faces, while also empowering them to adopt sustainable practices and participate in conservation efforts (Patra & Bhoi, 2025). Traditional conservation discussions are often presented in complex academic language, which can make them less accessible and less impactful for non-specialist audiences (Bennett *et al.*, 2017). In response, scholars have increasingly called for reframing conservation stories to better engage youth by using media and technology with compelling

storytelling, culturally relevant framing, and digital activism to create content that is accessible, meaningful, and widely impactful (Juppi, Pirita, 2017; Funk, Sascha, 2024). Youth-led conservation initiatives have demonstrated greater reach and impact compared to traditional top-down approaches. Vulli (2021) showed how the Save Bugoma Forest Campaign leveraged youth-driven environmental activism through digital media, using social media storytelling and online engagement to mobilize communities.

Similarly, Hajri, Oumaima, and Daife (2024) highlighted the role of social media in engaging young people in environmental issues through the #B7arBlaPlastic operation, organized by the Mohamed VI Foundation for Environmental Protection. Consequently, there is an increasing imperative to support youth as both content creators and science communicators, enabling them to translate conservation science into culturally resonant, media-savvy narratives that motivate conservation action. This aligns with broader observations on the promise and limits of digital activism in Africa, where digital media platforms offer new spaces for youth civic engagement but require adequate support and contextual relevance to maximize impact (Ndlela, 2020; UNESCO, 2022).

The rise of digital media and technology has opened new, effective avenues for sharing conservation science and education with larger and more diverse audiences. Platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, X (formerly Twitter), and blogs have transformed communication by enabling the instant delivery of interactive, visually engaging content. Formats like short videos, animations, infographics, memes, and blog posts make complex conservation topics more accessible and engaging, facilitating the rapid dissemination of science-based messages to broad audiences (Tazeen *et al.*, 2023; Han, 2024). These platforms also make content creation more inclusive, empowering non-experts especially youth—to tell stories that resonate with their cultural, linguistic, and generational contexts (Tazeen *et al.*, 2023). When harnessed by young people, these digital media and technology tools have the potential to significantly enhance conservation science outreach and impact.

Thus, this study highlights their potential as catalysts for advancing biodiversity conservation and promoting sustainable practices through youth-led digital campaigns. This study will examine how different digital media tools, storytelling, and social media platforms enable young people to translate conservation science into accessible and engaging forms that foster awareness, participation, and behavioural change. In doing so, the study assesses the effectiveness of different media formats and platforms, as well as audience perceptions of content quality, cultural relevance, and their influence on conservation engagement.

METHODOLOGY

Study Duration Period: This study was conducted from May to July 2025.

Study Area: This study was conducted at the University of Lagos, Nigeria, a major urban academic institution located in the South-West region of the country. The University of Lagos had a student enrollment of approximately 35,068 in the 2024/2025 academic year (University of Lagos, Statistics, 2024) and an annual growth rate of about 2.7–2.8%. This steady expansion has placed significant pressure on infrastructure, green spaces, and biodiversity. Beyond its population size, the University of Lagos’s strategic location within a biodiversity-rich region—home to mangrove ecosystems, wetlands, and coastal habitats—makes it not only a hub for youth engagement and digital innovation but also an ideal setting for exploring how young people can leverage media and technology to advance conservation education.

Study Design: This study adopted an exploratory, practice-based design, a methodological approach particularly suited to generating applied insights through active participation and experiential learning (McNiff & Whitehead, 2006; Lewandowska, 2024). This design enabled students to acquire practical skills while simultaneously applying their learning in real-world conservation outreach, aligning with practice-based approaches that emphasize experiential learning, co-creation, and iterative reflection (Kemmis *et al.*, 2014).

A purposive sample of 50 students from the Society for Ecological Restoration, University of Lagos Student Chapter, was recruited to participate in a two-week training programme aimed at developing digital communication skills for conservation education. Participants were selected based on their interest in conservation, availability to engage in the study, and potential to act as multipliers of conservation messages within their networks. The training provided students with the technical and creative competencies necessary to produce high-quality, engaging conservation content.

After the training, participants used their skills in a 30-day campaign focused on pangolin conservation, creating and sharing content across social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter (X), YouTube, and WordPress, as shown in **(Box 1)**. They used various media formats, including short videos, reels, animations, posters, and blog articles, to make sure their messages were visually appealing and accessible to a broad audience.

The campaign's impact was evaluated using a combination of social media platform analytics and embedded audience feedback forms. Analytics captured quantitative measures of engagement such as reach, views, likes, shares, and comments, while feedback forms collected qualitative and semi-quantitative responses to assess audience perceptions and the potential influence of content on conservation-related attitudes and behaviours. This integrated approach facilitated an assessment not only of students' acquisition and application of digital media but also of the effectiveness of their outputs and the extent to which audience engagement reflected heightened awareness, participation, and potential behavioural change in relation to conservation as shown in the core objectives of the study **(Box 2)**

Box 1. Training Modules	
Module	Focus Area
Photography /Graphics Design	Photography basics, visual storytelling, and creating awareness posters, flyers and Banners using Canva.
Video Editing & Animation	Editing with InShot and creating animations with FlipaClip to produce engaging audiovisual materials.
Blog Creation	Web content development on WordPress for publishing articles and conservation stories.
Script Writing & Content Planning	Drafting concise, platform-specific scripts for video and animation content.
Social Media Strategy	Strategic post scheduling, audience targeting, hashtag optimization, and cross-platform coordination.

- | Box 2: Core Objectives of Study |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To evaluate the effectiveness of different media formats (short videos, reels, animations, posters, blog articles) in promoting conservation awareness. • To identify the primary channels through which the audience encounters conservation content and evaluate their relative impact on engagement. • To analyze respondents' perceptions of content quality and its capacity to raise awareness and concern about conservation. • To assess the willingness of respondents to engage with and support conservation content in the future. • To engage youth in conservation education using media and technology to promote awareness and action. |

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted concurrently with the 30-day content dissemination campaign. Two primary sources of data were used to capture both audience engagement and perceptions of the conservation content.

Platform Analytics

Quantitative metrics were extracted from each social media platform used in the campaign, including Instagram, Twitter (X), YouTube, and WordPress. The analytics collected included the number of views, likes, shares, comments, and reach for each post. These metrics were recorded weekly throughout the campaign to ensure consistency and monitor trends over time. Platform-specific tools were used to collect these data: Instagram Insights, Twitter/X Analytics, YouTube Studio, and Jetpack for WordPress. These metrics allowed for assessment of engagement by media type (short videos, reels, animations, posters, blog articles) and performance across platforms, providing a basis for comparing the effectiveness of different content formats and delivery channels.

Platform analytics data were processed using SPSS to calculate descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and proportions for metrics like views, likes, comments, and shares. Engagement was analyzed by media type (short videos, reels, animations, posters, blogs) and by social media platform (Instagram, Twitter/X, YouTube, WordPress), directly mirroring the results for Engagement Metrics, Performance Analysis, and Content Engagement. Comparative analysis identified which media formats and platforms drove the highest reach, interaction, and audience sharing behaviors.

Audience Feedback Forms

To capture qualitative and semi-quantitative data on user perceptions, embedded feedback forms were attached to posts across all platforms. The forms collected information on respondents' demographic characteristics (age, gender, occupation, and geographic location), channels through which they encountered the content, interaction behaviors (likes, comments, shares), emotional responses, perceived content quality, cultural relevance, and willingness to engage with or support conservation content in the future. In total, 161 respondents completed the survey forms during the campaign period.

Responses from the audience feedback forms were analyzed to identify patterns in perception, emotional response, and behavioural intention. Quantitative data were summarized to calculate percentages of positive, neutral, and negative responses for content quality, awareness impact, and willingness to support conservation. This mirrored the results on respondent perception and emotional response, allowing for direct comparison between analytics metrics and audience-reported engagement.

RESULTS

Audience Respondent Numbers and Survey Locations.

A. Audience Feedback and Analytics

Audience Perception and Engagement: Insights A Total of 161 respondents completed the survey form linked to the campaign content across all dissemination platforms (Table 1). An analysis of respondent distribution by location at the time of data collection, based on self-reported city, state, and country, revealed a notable concentration in the South-West region of Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State (Figure 1). Analysis of demographic characteristics revealed that the audience was predominantly composed of young adults, with male and female participants represented in nearly equal proportions (Table 1).

Figure 1. Map indicating the geographic distribution of all survey respondents, with red markers representing the city and State of Respondents

Table 1. Demography of Respondents (n=161)

Basic Information	Category	Frequency of Audience Feedback	Percentage
Age	Under 18	21	13.0%
	18–29	78	48.4%
	30–44	41	25.5%
	45+	21	13.0%
Gender	Male	77	47.8%
	Female	84	52.2%
Occupation	Student	79	49.1%
	Self-employed	48	29.8%
	Employed	34	21.1%

Students formed the largest segment of respondents, underscoring the campaign’s strong resonance with youth and academic communities. This dominance may be linked to social media platforms’ use of algorithms and location-based proximity in delivering content and post feeds, which increases visibility within nearby networks. It may also be influenced by referral networks created through those who shared the post (Table 2). South-East, South-South, and North had more minor but notable representations, as shown in Figure 1.

Content Engagement

Content was primarily encountered through interpersonal sharing, followed by social media feeds, with minimal discovery via websites or search engines (Table 2). Short videos and reels emerged as the audience’s preferred content format, followed by animations, posters/graphics, and blog articles (Table 2). This pattern reflects earlier findings (Figure 2), where short videos and animations were identified as the most effective formats in terms of reach and interaction.

Most respondents (62.7%) confirmed that they viewed the content and actively engaged with it through likes, comments, or shares. A smaller proportion (30.4%) reported no interaction at all, while 6.8% indicated that they had viewed the content but did not engage. These findings highlight that the majority of the audience demonstrated active participation rather than passive consumption. The perceived reasons for non-engagement are outlined in (Box 3)

Table 2. Respondents’ Content Access Channels and Preferred Content Formats

Category	Source/Format	Frequency	Percentage
Primary Channels Through Which Respondents Encountered the Content	WhatsApp	47	29.2%
	Social media post feed	28	17.4%
	Shared post link from family & friends	86	53.4%
	Total	161	100%
Respondent Engagement by Media Type.	Poster/Graphics	40	22.7%
	Short videos/Reels	75	42.6%
	Animation	52	29.5%
	Blog Article	9	5.1%
	Total	176	100%

Perception and Emotional Response

Evaluation of the campaign content revealed a highly positive reception. A large majority of respondents (78.3%) rated the content as good, while 16.8% described it as excellent. Only 5.0% rated it as fair, and none considered it poor (Table 2). These findings indicate that the overall quality of the content was widely appreciated

When asked whether the content made them feel more aware and concerned about conservation issues, 85.7% of respondents affirmed that it did, while 1.2% indicated no, and 13.0% responded that it did to some extent (Table 3). This highlights the effectiveness of the campaign in fostering awareness and concern.

Future willingness to engage with conservation content was also strong. On a five-point scale, 16.1% selected the highest level (very likely), while 66.5% indicated level 4, suggesting high readiness to support conservation initiatives in the future. Lower levels of willingness were rare, with only 14.3% choosing level 3, and fewer than 4% selecting levels 1 or 2 (Table 3). This pattern demonstrates not only immediate resonance of the campaign but also its potential to inspire long-term commitment.

Table 3. Audience Perceptions of Content Quality, Awareness, and Future Support

Category	Response/Scale	Percentage
Content Quality Rating	Excellent	16.8%
	Good	78.3%
	Fair	5.0%
	Poor	0.0%
Awareness and Concern	Yes	85.7%
	No	1.2%
	Somehow	13.0%
Likelihood of Supporting Content in Future	1 – Not likely	1.2%
	2	7.5%
	3	14.3%
	4	66.5%
	5 – Very likely	16.1%
Total		100%

B. Engagement Metrics/Analytics

Engagement Metrics Across Media Type

Short Videos/Reels

Short videos and reels generated the highest overall visibility, with 1,500 total views across Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter (Figure 2a). YouTube contributed the largest proportion (800 views; 53.3%), followed by Instagram (500 views; 33.3%) and Twitter (200 views; 13.3%). Engagement patterns reflect platform-specific strengths: YouTube produced the highest number of likes (65; 44.5%) and comments (20; 51.3%), highlighting its capacity for evaluative interaction. Instagram, however, drove the majority of shares (25 out of 63 total; 39.7%), highlighting its role in peer-to-peer amplification. Twitter contributed moderately but consistently, accounting for 20 likes, 5 comments, and 8 shares. Collectively, short videos functioned as the most effective awareness driver, balancing reach with measurable engagement.

Graphic Posters

Graphic posters achieved a total of 800 views, with Instagram generating the largest share (400 views; 50%), followed by Twitter (250 views; 31.3%) and YouTube (150 views; 18.7%) (Figure 2b). Posters yielded 83 likes, 19 comments, and 14 shares. Instagram performed strongest, producing 50 likes (60.2%), confirming its efficiency in hosting static visuals. Twitter also contributed a moderate number of likes (25) and comments (6), while YouTube engagement remained minimal (8 likes, 3 comments, no shares). This trend demonstrates that while posters serve effectively as quick, data-efficient content for audiences mindful of mobile data use, their potential for virality or sustained dialogue is limited, especially on video-dominant platforms.

Animations

Animations recorded 1,000 total views, with YouTube again dominant (600 views; 60%), followed by Instagram (300 views; 30%) and Twitter (100 views; 10%) (Figure 2c). Engagement reached 110 likes, 33 comments, and 37 shares. YouTube hosted the largest share of likes (55; 50%), comments (18; 54.5%), and shares (20; 54.1%), confirming its role in fostering evaluation and sustained attention. Instagram, however, showed stronger proportional interaction, contributing 45 likes, 12 comments, and 15 shares, despite having a lower reach. Twitter recorded modest but consistent participation. These findings suggest that animations, though less widely disseminated than short videos, offer an effective balance of storytelling depth and interactivity, particularly among already-engaged audiences.

Blogs (WordPress)

Blogs on WordPress generated 200 views, marking the lowest visibility of all formats. Engagement was correspondingly modest, with 10 likes, 5 comments, and 5 shares (Figure 2d). This reflects the nature of long-form content: while valuable for deepening understanding among niche audiences, blogs are less effective in driving broad awareness or viral interaction. Their role is therefore complementary supporting the dissemination of detailed knowledge but secondary in campaigns aiming for large-scale public engagement.

Figure 2(a-d). Engagement Metrics Across Media Types (Short Videos/Reels, Graphic Posters, Animations, and WordPress Blogs) based on analytics from Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and Wordpress.

Performance Analysis of Social Media Platform

Long-form visual formats, such as animations and detailed videos, were most effective in achieving broad awareness, as seen on YouTube, which accounted for the highest number of views and evaluative interactions. In contrast, short and visually rich formats, such as reels and posters, were more effective in driving active peer-to-peer interaction, as observed on Instagram, where sharing and immediate audience responses were most prominent. Blogs, as seen on Wordpress, complemented these formats by providing substantive and contextual information, although their overall reach was comparatively limited (Figure 3).

Box 3: Suggestions and Comments

- The main reasons respondents gave for viewing content without interacting were a lack of interest and not being in the mood to engage. This highlights that non-interaction was less about content accessibility or quality and more about personal disposition at the time of viewing, as shown in **(Table 2)**.
- Many respondents expressed satisfaction with the conservation content, praising its relevance and appeal. They suggested that such content should be produced consistently, indicating that regular exposure would likely encourage continued and potentially increased engagement in the future.
- A good percentage of the respondents proposed incorporating interactive elements such as quizzes, polls, or short challenges to make the content more engaging and memorable.

Figure 3. Performance Analysis by Social Media Platform

DISCUSSION

Youth engagement is a critical component of effective conservation education, particularly when it is integrated with modern media and technology. By actively participating in this study, the youth not only contributed to content creation but also acted as co-communicators of conservation science, bridging the gap between expert knowledge and public understanding. Their familiarity with digital tools and social platforms positioned them to design, adapt, and disseminate messages in formats and styles that align with contemporary consumption habits (Duran-Becerra, 2020).

The study demonstrates that both content format and technology-enabled delivery play a decisive role in driving conservation engagement among young audiences. Short videos and reels were the most effective formats, producing the highest reach and interaction, with YouTube excelling in likes and comments, and Instagram leading in shares. Animations followed closely, leveraging storytelling techniques that simplified complex pangolin conservation messages for broad audiences. In contrast, posters and graphics attracted individuals who were more mindful of mobile data consumption, but they were less successful in stimulating wider interaction, while blog articles appealed mainly to niche, pre-engaged readers (Haddock, 2022).

The study revealed that interpersonal sharing and organic discovery through social media feeds were the main channels of exposure, highlighting the importance of shareability and peer-to-peer dissemination in broadening audience reach. Similar trends have been observed in other youth-led conservation initiatives across Africa. For example, Wildaboutlife in Kenya demonstrated the viral potential of youth-generated short videos, while the FAO's AIM4Forests program in Kenya and Uganda showed how combining digital content with on-the-ground youth action can foster deeper and more sustained engagement. Comparable patterns emerge globally: Cruz Crespo and Cruz (2023) reported that social media activism for bee conservation stimulated offline community participation, illustrating how digital initiatives can drive tangible real-world outcomes. Likewise, Bergman *et al.* (2022) emphasize that, despite certain risks, carefully curated wildlife content on social media can positively shape public attitudes and encourage pro-conservation behaviors.

In line with these studies, audience feedback from our research was overwhelmingly positive: most respondents rated the content as “Good” or “Excellent,” and their comments reflected heightened awareness and concern (see **Box 3**)

CONCLUSION This study demonstrates the effectiveness of youth-led digital media campaigns in advancing conservation education and awareness. By equipping young people with practical communication skills, conservation messages were delivered in engaging formats that reached diverse audiences and stimulated positive perceptions and willingness to act. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of youth as active co-creators of conservation knowledge and advocates for biodiversity protection when empowered with technology and creative tools. Future initiatives should prioritize sustained training opportunities for young people, extend the reach of such campaigns, and embed conservation education more firmly within both formal and informal learning contexts.

REFERENCES

- Bergman, J., Buxton, R., Lin, H.-Y., Lenda, M., Attinello, K., Hajdasz, A., Rivest, S., Tran Nguyen, T., Cooke, S., & Bennett, J. (2022). Evaluating the benefits and risks of social media for wildlife conservation. *FACETS*, 7, 360–397. <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2021-0112>
- Cruz Crespo, Y., & Cruz, S. (2023). The role of social media activism in offline conservation attitudes And behaviors. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 174, 107858. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107858>
- Duran-Becerra, B. (2020). Climate change on YouTube: A potential platform for youth engagement. *PMC*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7420161/>
- Funk, S. (2024). Empowering voices, shaping futures: Digital storytelling for sustainable transformation. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 13, 1345–1359. <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2024.13.1.1827>
- Haddock, A. (2022). Positive effects of digital technology use by adolescents. *PMC*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9658971/>
- Hajri, O., & Daife, Y. (2024). The role of social media in engaging young people in environmental issues. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 477, 00079. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202447700079>
- Han, L. (2024). The rise of digital media: Transforming communication, culture, and commerce. *Global Media Journal*, 22(72), 472.
- Juppi, P. (2017). Engagement and empowerment: Digital storytelling as a participatory media practice. *Nordicom Review*, 39.
- Kamau, S. (2016). Engaged online: social media and youth civic engagement in Kenya. Springer International Publishing, 115–140. https://ecommons.aku.edu/eastafrika_gsmc/17
- Lewandowska, K. (2024). Practice-based research in the social sciences & humanities: A bibliometric analysis. *Iberoamerican Journal of Science Measurement and Communication*, 4(3), 1–16.
- McNiff, J., & Whitehead, J. (2006). All you need to know about action research. SAGE Publications.
- Ndlela, M. (2020). Young people, social media, and political participation: The limits of discursive(in)civility in the Kenyan context. In *Political Participation and Social Media* (pp. 89–108). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32682-1_5
- Patra, B., & Bhoi, C. (2025). Nurturing green minds: The role of education in environmental conservation. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 13(2), a370. <https://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2502045.pdf>
- Tazeen, F., & Mullick, N. (2023). The impact of social media platforms, Facebook and Instagram, in influencing purchasing behaviour of green products. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629221133960>
- UNESCO. (2022). Youth and environmental sustainability: Digital platforms as tools for engagement. UNESCO Publishing. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379843>

- University of Lagos. (2024). UNILAG statistics. <https://unilag.edu.ng/unilag-statistics/>
- USDA. (2023). Conservation education. United States Department of Agriculture, Forest Service. <https://research.fs.usda.gov/pnw/about/conservationeducation>
- Vulli, A. (2021). Environmental activism in the age of digital media: Netnography of Save Bugoma Forest Campaign (Dissertation). <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:su:diva-202520>

© abubakar ringin

©2025